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Transformational Leadership Style and Employee Job Satisfaction

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Abstract

By exercising leadership, a person tries to persuade other group members to work toward shared objectives. Another way to look at leadership is as a tool that individuals use to bring out the best in one another and themselves. The degree to which current leadership philosophies are related to job satisfaction varies. Numerous studies have shown that transformational leadership, as opposed to transactional or laissez-faire leadership, results in better levels of job satisfaction. The overall aim of the study was to investigate the impact of Transformational Leadership Style on employee job satisfaction of government employees in divisional secretariats in Nuwara-Eliya District. Data from 150 respondents were collected through a structured questionnaire and analyzed using SPSS. This study employed the regression analysis method to assess the significant influence of leadership style. The findings showed that transformational leadership significantly explained 55.2% of the variance in job satisfaction. Furthermore, a positive correlation was observed between transformational leadership style and job happiness. These results underscore the importance of leadership style in shaping job satisfaction among government employees in divisional secretariats. Further research directions are proposed to deepen the understanding of the underlying mechanisms and boundary conditions of this relationship, thus providing practical insights for effective leadership practices and employee well-being.

Keywords: Transformational Leadership Style, Employee Job Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Transformational leadership style has emerged as a crucial factor in shaping employee job satisfaction and organizational success. With increasing recognition of the importance of employee well-being and motivation, organizations are seeking effective leadership approaches that can enhance job satisfaction and overall performance. Transformational leadership, characterized by visionary, inspirational, and charismatic leadership behaviors, has gained substantial attention in the field of organizational behavior and management.

According to Bass and Riggio (2006), transformational leaders have the ability to inspire and motivate their followers to exceed their own self-interests and pursue collective goals. They stimulate creativity, encourage innovation, and foster a sense of purpose and meaning among employees. Through their actions and behaviors, transformational leaders create an environment that promotes employee growth, development, and satisfaction.

Employee job satisfaction, a key construct in organizational behavior, refers to the overall positive affective and cognitive evaluations that employees have regarding their job experiences (Locke, 1976). Job satisfaction has been linked to a range of favorable outcomes, including increased employee engagement, higher productivity, lower turnover rates, and improved organizational performance (Judge et al., 2001).

The relationship between transformational leadership style and employee job satisfaction has been widely studied in the literature. Numerous empirical studies have reported positive associations between these two constructs. For example, a study by Avolio et al. (2004) found that transformational leadership behaviors positively influenced employee job satisfaction in a sample of healthcare professionals. Similarly, Podsakoff et al. (2014) conducted a meta-analysis and confirmed a positive relationship between transformational leadership and employee job satisfaction across various industries and settings.

The mechanisms through which transformational leadership enhances employee job satisfaction have also been explored. Transformational leaders inspire and motivate employees by providing a clear vision, setting high expectations, and offering individualized support and mentoring (Bass and Riggio, 2006). They empower employees by delegating authority and involving them in decision-making processes, which fosters a sense of ownership and autonomy. Moreover, transformational leaders create opportunities for personal and professional growth, allowing employees to develop their skills and reach their full potential (Bass and Riggio, 2006).

While the existing literature highlights the positive relationship between transformational leadership style and employee job satisfaction, there are also factors that may moderate this relationship. Organizational culture, employee demographics, and job characteristics have been identified as potential moderators (Bass and Riggio, 2006). For instance, an organizational culture that values innovation and collaboration may strengthen the impact of transformational leadership on employee job satisfaction. Similarly, the effects of transformational leadership may vary across different demographic groups, such as gender or tenure. Job characteristics, such as autonomy and task significance, may also influence the relationship between transformational leadership and job satisfaction.

Therefore, this research paper aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between transformational leadership style and employee job satisfaction. By conducting a systematic literature review, we will examine the existing empirical evidence and theoretical frameworks that support this relationship. Additionally, we will explore the mechanisms through which transformational leadership influences employee job satisfaction and identify potential moderating factors. The findings of this study will have practical implications for organizational leaders and human resource practitioners, providing insights into effective leadership practices that enhance employee job satisfaction and contribute to overall organizational success.

The following specific research questions are the purpose of the study:

1. What is the level of job satisfaction among staff members in the divisional secretariats in Nuwara-Eliya District?
2. Does transformational leadership have an impact on the job satisfaction of employees in divisional secretariats in Nuwara-Eliya District?
3. What recommendations can be proposed to enhance employees' job satisfaction through leadership styles in divisional secretariats in Nuwara-Eliya District?

2. literature review

2.1. Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction was described by Schermerhorn (1993) as a rational or emotional reaction to a number of work-related factors. Also described as an emotional response to one's duties and working environment, as well as the degree to which one's expectations are met (Kreitner and Kinicki, 2009). It can be broadly characterized as the level of job satisfaction among employees (Mester et al., 2003:72). According to Davis et al. (1985), an individual's behavior at work is directly related to their job satisfaction. According to Porter, Steers, Mowday, and Boulian (1974), job satisfaction refers to how a person feels about his or her employment in terms of income, advancement, supervision, and the actual labor. High levels of job satisfaction are linked to lower levels of stress, greater levels of empowerment, higher levels of production, and organizational growth.

Since most people spend their entire lives at work, understanding the factors that increase satisfaction is crucial to enhancing people's wellbeing in this area of living (Gruneberg, 1997), many theories and articles of interest to managers, social psychologists, and scholars center on job satisfaction. Between the 1960s and 1970s, 4,000 research on job satisfaction were published. Later, this number increased to 12,000 publications (Locke, 1976; Ghawazzi, 2008).

We believe that a sense of job satisfaction results from the belief that one's work satisfies both their physical and psychological demands (Aziri, 2008). According to Richmond, McCroskey, and Davis (1982), "extremely satisfied employees may form the type of work group known as the "happiness for lunch bunch" (McCroskey, Larson and Knapp, 1971) and be more of a social group than a work group, lowering productivity. Moderately satisfied employees may be more productive than dissatisfied employees.

2.2. Leadership and Transformational Leadership

The act of leading a group of individuals toward the accomplishment of a stated objective is known as leadership. To bring about beneficial change within the firm, one must master the skill of inspiring, persuading, and motivating others. Leadership is one of the most observed and least understood phenomena on earth, according to researcher J. M. Burns. The attempt to define the term "leadership" has proven to be difficult for both academics and practitioners alike, (2002) Zenger and Folkman. According to Smylie et al. (2005), someone who performs leadership must have certain duties and task-oriented viewpoints. Leadership also plays a crucial "function" in interactions with other leaders, followers, and circumstances. As defined by Cojocar (2008), leadership is the capacity of an individual to exert influence over and provide opportunities for others to make commitments to the effectiveness and success of the organizations in which they engage.

Downton (1973), Burns (1978), and Bryman (1992) were the first to advocate transformational leadership; it was later developed by Bass and Riggio (2006) and Avolio and Gardner (2005). Burns made a distinction between transformational leadership and a more conventional transactional method in 1978. A transformational leader inspires and inspires others, bringing about change within an organization (Burns, 1978; Weber, 2009). According to Cavazotte, Moreno, and Hickmann (2012), leadership effectiveness has a direct impact on the transformative behaviors of leaders and a direct indirect impact on employee intelligence and experience. The goal of transformational leadership, according to Bass, is to "transform" people and organizations in an actual way – to change them in the mind and heart, enlarge vision, insight, and understanding, clarify reasons, and make behavior consistent with values and concepts (Nanjundeswaraswamy and Swamy, 2014).

According to Warrick (2011), modern organizational changes A transformational leader is essential because they may rebuild an organization's structure to suit their needs. However, this idea needs to be promoted since few businesses are accustomed with this type of leadership. Additionally, the study conducted by Choi et al. (2016) in Malaysian hospitals demonstrates how empowerment and transformational leadership have an impact on employee job satisfaction. Employee satisfaction is highest, according to Adler and Reid (2008:26), when the leader is encouraging and thoughtful. Transformational leadership is a process whereby a strong personal identification is maintained with the leader, according to Ozaralli (2002:335).

The main attributes that form the basis of effective transformational leadership are described below.

2.2.1. Ideolised Influence

Ideolised influence focuses on the creation and expression of a vision and difficult aims, as well as inspiring followers to put aside their own interests in order to strive toward shared objectives (Dionne, Yammarino, Atwater and Spangler, 2004). In this fashion, followers want to mimic or copy them since they view them as role models (Khaola, 2019). Leaders also serve as role models for their followers, earning their admiration, respect, and trust. High standards of moral and ethical behavior are displayed by leaders with significant ideological impact, who are also prepared to take risks and are consistent rather than arbitrary (Bass and Riggio, 2006). When a leader makes important judgments under pressure and displays conviction and confidence, ideological influence is at work (Nielsen, Yarker, Brenner, Randall, and Borg, 2008:467).

Followers are inspired by role models to take measured risks while resolving complex situations and see how they might develop into more responsible and self-assured people. Ozaralli (2002:335) also refers to ideological influence as a process in which the leader inspires followers to have faith, pride, and respect in

themselves. Initiatives in coaching and mentoring promote autonomy in decision-making within a supportive setting. According to Antonakis, Avolio, and Sivasubramaniam (2003), leaders share risk with followers and sacrifice their own interests in order to help followers.

2.2.2. Intellectual stimulation

By challenging presumptions and treating familiar circumstances in novel ways, leaders can encourage innovation and creativity in their followers (Bass and Riggio, 2006; Nicholason, 2007). This is known as intellectual stimulation. They always exhort their followers to experiment with fresh ideas or techniques in order to address persistent issues. When a leader fosters followers' creativity to explore for novel and more effective problem-solving techniques than those previously used, intellectual stimulation results (Mester et al., 2003:73). Leaders encourage employee engagement in decision-making, look for various options, and let the staff select the best ones to address issues and reach decisions (Bass and Avolio, 2002; Nicolaidis, 2008; 2019). In order to promote deeper and more creative thinking, the leader challenges followers to think beyond the box and explore other possibilities (Barling, Comotis, Gatien, Kelloway and Kelly, 2003:163). When the status quo is questioned, followers' thinking capacities improve. This process leads to new revelations and insights among followers, raising their standards for success. The inventive thought process is aided by the use of problem-solving and brainstorming approaches (Roland Loganathan, 2013).

2.2.3. Individualized Consideration

According to Bass and Riggio (2006) and Nicholason (2007), leaders who practice individualized consideration provide extra thought to each follower's desire for development and success. They do this by serving as a coach or mentor. According to Mester et al. (2003:73), personalized consideration is a process in which the leader recognizes each person's individuality, connects those needs to the needs of the business, and offers coaching, mentoring, and growth opportunities. Effective leaders must show that they care about their followers' particular needs and meet those needs accordingly. Additionally, this leadership style uses both upstream and downstream communication to close the communication gap (Khan et al., 2018; Mukezakule, 2019). The fact that individual requirements, expectations, and skill and experience levels differ greatly is a frequent conclusion. In order to understand followers personally and respond to their issues strategically, an interpersonal connection is essential. Individualized Consideration (IC), which is defined as the manifestation of open concern for their subordinates' needs and feelings, pays attention to each person on an individual basis and prioritizes their best efforts for increased organizational effectiveness and performance in achieving the objectives (Krishnan, 2005). The leader fulfils the role of a listener who attentively identifies the strengths, limitations, and development potentials of people in order to foster a supportive and caring environment. The leader's goal is to support each person's personal growth while looking for ways to support them in achieving their goals. Through the process of delegated authority, leaders enable followers to develop through personal obstacles (Roland Loganathan, 2013).

2.2.4. Inspirational motivation

By providing followers with a challenge and a shared meaning, inspirational motivation uses behaviour to inspire and motivate staff members (McCleskey, 2014). This means that it is a characteristic of leaders that act in a way that motivates others by pushing their team members and setting clear expectations for them (Bass et al., 2006). The leader provides purpose and a sense of challenge that inspires and drives the team members' work. By integrating them in a good future vision and by articulating high expectations that followers desire to attain, the leader fosters team spirit, passion, and optimism among their followers (Gomes, 2014). The leader also promotes adherence to the organization's mission and shared values (Bass et al., 2006).

Research Methodology

In light of the prior research, the goal of this research is to create a theoretical framework to examine the connection between a transformational leadership style and job satisfaction.

The theoretical structure demonstrates the link between Transformational leadership style (independent variables) and worker job satisfaction (dependent variable). According to the literature review, there is just one leadership style used by the researcher.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Developed for the research purpose, 2023

The following hypothesis was formed based on the conceptual framework mentioned above and the literature review.

H1: Transformational leadership has a significant impact on job satisfaction.

3.2. Data collection procedure

In the current study, the data were collected from the 150 respondents through a personally administered structured questionnaire. The respondents were government employees of the divisional secretariats. The data was collected from five divisional secretariats of Nuwara – Eliya District. Such as Ambagamuwa, Nuwera Eliya, Hangurketha, Kothmale and Walapane. The pilot test was conducted from the sampling population. Hundred and fifty employees were taken as the sample of this study by using simple random sampling method.

3.3. Measures of Variables

The data collected from the questionnaire were carefully coded and checked for the consistency and entered in to SPSS spreadsheet. The descriptive statistics included the frequency and the percentage of the frequency for all variables. SPSS package version 21 was used to analyze the data of this study. Moreover, measures of central tendency (mean, standard deviation) were used to analyze the questionnaire survey result.

In total, two variables—leadership style and work satisfaction—were examined in this study. The personnel of the divisional secretariats in the Nuwara-Eliya District were given the questionnaire. The sampling population served as the basis for the pilot test. Pilot studies also allow the researcher to assess the effectiveness of the flow of the instructions (Bryman and Bell, 2007:274).

4. Data Analysis and Presentatio

The overall response rate was 96%. Analyzing the respondents' demographics revealed that women made up the majority of the respondents. Additionally, the majority of the divisional secretariats were Development officers with ages ranging from 26 to 35 and an average experience of 5-7 years.

Table 4.1: Cronbatch alpha value of variables

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Cronbatch alpha</i>
Transformational leadership style	0.834
Job satisfaction	0.774

(Source: Survey data, 2023)

To evaluate the instrument's internal consistency and dependability, Cronbach alpha was also developed. The Cronbach alpha, which is 0.890 for all variables, is shown in Table 4.1. It ensured that the products' internal consistency was reliable as a result.

Table 4.2: Cronbach alpha Reliability Statistic

Cronbach's Alpha	No of Items
.890	2

(Source: Survey data, 2023)

Using SPSS version 21.0, the research variables of transformational leadership styles and job satisfaction were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation.

The mean, the standard deviation, the minimum value, and the highest value for each variable are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Descriptive Statistics of Research Variables

Variables	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Standard deviation
Intellectual stimulation	144	1	5	2.84	0.018
Idealized influence	144	1	5	3.06	0.009
Individualized consideration	144	1	5	3.08	0.051
Inspirational motivation	144	1	5	3.03	0.200
Transformational Leadership Style				3.00	0.157
Intrinsic	144	1	5	2.97	0.910
Extrinsic	144	1	5	3.10	0.225
Job Satisfaction				3.03	0.458

(Source: Survey Data, 2023)

The mean value of the descriptive statistics summarized in Table 4.3 indicates that transformational leadership is used at a modest level in the divisional secretariats of the Nuwara Eliya district. Like inspiration for motivation 3.03, Individualized consideration 3.08, idealized influence 3.06 and intellectual stimulation 2.84. According to the job satisfaction index, intrinsic contentment is moderately high at 2.97 and extrinsic satisfaction is moderately high at 3.10 (3.03). This information leads the researcher to the conclusion that the Nuwara-Eliya district's Divisional Secretariats have a Moderate level of job satisfaction.

4.1 Hypothesis 1:

Transformational leadership has a significant impact on job satisfaction.

Regression analysis was utilized to determine the effect of transformational leadership style on work satisfaction. Table 4.4 displays the results in a condensed format.

Table 4.4: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.743 ^a	.552	.549	.588

Predictors: (Constant), Transformational leadership style

(Source: Survey Data,2023)

The results suggest that the predictor variable (Transformational Leadership style) explain 55.2% of the variance in Job satisfaction. Moreover, the adjusted R= .743^a.

Table 4.5: ANOVA^a

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Regression	60.632	1	60.632	175.207	.000 ^b
Residual	49.141	142	.346		
Total	109.773	143			

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Transformational leadership style

(Source: Survey Data,2023)

Table 4.6: Coefficients

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	.743	.176		4.232	.000
Transformational leadership style	.743	.056	.743	13.237	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job satisfaction

(Source: Survey Data, 2023)

The P value is 0.000, as can be seen in the coefficient's graphs. P value here is less than 0.005. as a results, the transformational leadership style has a big impact on job satisfaction. H1 gets approved as a result.

3. Findings and Conclusions

The purpose of the current study is to determine whether the leadership style (transformational leadership style) has a substantial effect on the job satisfaction of public employees in divisional secretariats in the Nuwara-eliya district. In order to explore in the current study, the following research objectives have been developed:

1. To investigate the current level of employee's job satisfaction of divisional secretariats in Nuwara – Eliya District
2. To identify the impact of transformational leadership styles on employees' job satisfaction of divisional secretariats in Nuwara – Eliya District.
3. To provide recommendations for improve employees' job satisfaction through leadership styles in divisional secretariats in Nuwara - Eliya District.

To address the research topics, one hypothesis was developed for this study. Divisional secretariats in the Nuwara-eliya District served as the population sample for this study. Ambagamuwa, Nuwera Eliya, Hangurnketha, Kothmale, and Walapane are just a few of the five Divisional Secretary's Divisions that make up the Nuwera-Eliya District. Then, using the simple random selection approach, a sample of 150 people was chosen from a set of 5 divisions within the Nuwara-eliya area.

The researcher also adopted the 11 job satisfaction items (Xianyin Lee, Boxu Yang, and Wendong Li, et al., 2017) and the 21 items developed to measure the level of leadership style on job satisfaction (Mitzi N. Stumpf, et al., 2003) for the current study. Data were gathered using a structured questionnaire procedure. Descriptive analysis was used to examine respondent demographics. Additionally, using SPSS version 21.0 software, regression analysis was used to test the model and the proposed hypotheses.

96% of respondents responded in total. The majority of respondents were female, according to the examination of the respondent demographics. In addition, most of the divisional secretariats were Development officers with an average experience of 5-7 years, and they were primarily under the age of 35 and 26.

The study found that factor loadings (reliability), content validity, and convergent validity were all at satisfactory levels. Additionally, the regression analysis supported the model established by the coefficient of determination (R²), which demonstrated that the variance in job satisfaction is significantly explained (55.2%) by two variables (transformational leadership style). Additionally, a moderate association exists between leadership style (transformational leadership style) and job happiness. It was discovered that work happiness and transformational leadership style had important favorable links. Conclusion: Job satisfaction is greatly impacted by leadership style (transformational leadership style).

4. Direction for future research

Even while the current study's findings, based on the conceptual model used in this study, offered new insight, they also suggested a direction for future research. The current study's primary goal was to investigate the influence of leadership style on job satisfaction among public employees working in divisional secretariats in the Nuwara-eliya district. As a result, it did not concentrate on all of Sri Lanka's Divisions. The investigation of a larger spectrum of workers in other divisional secretariats in Sri Lanka may also be beneficial for this research.

Further qualitative study should be conducted to better understand the impact of leadership style on employee job satisfaction. because the majority of responders weren't sure of their response. Because of this, these qualitative factors might reduce this form of uncertainty. Therefore, in the future, researchers should combine surveys and interview sessions to obtain more thorough results. Data should be gathered from more respondents from the organizations in order to improve external validity and broaden the applicability of the findings.

The researchers noted that a variety of organizationally significant factors, including pay, advancement opportunities, fringe benefits, job security, relationships with coworkers and managers, work environment, safety and security, flexibility, and initiative and leadership, all have an impact on job satisfaction. Additionally, the scope of the current study is restricted to looking at how one leadership style—transformational leadership—affects job satisfaction. When examining the suggested model, a number of other leadership styles (transactional, authoritarian, democratic, and laissez-faire leadership) that are also associated to job satisfaction were disregarded. Future research may therefore take into account additional relevant variables that affect job satisfaction.

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